

Comparative Studies on Physicochemical and Bacteriological Analysis of the Various Sources of Drinking Water Made Available for Cadets of Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano, Nigeria

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Abstract: - Portable water is defined as water that is fit for human consumption. Drinking Water must be safe and devoid of pathogenic microorganisms, toxins and anything that can be hazardous to human health. The aim of this study is to determine the safety and suitability of the various sources of drinking water (sachet, bottled and borehole) available to cadets of Nigeria Police Academy. 16 water samples (4 each of sachet, bottled and borehole) were collected for physicochemical and bacteriological analysis using standard methods. The Physicochemical parameters (pH, Dissolved Carbon dioxide, Total hardness, Total Dissolved Solids and Nitrate content) of all the water sources were within the World Health Organization (WHO) standards with the exception of Total alkalinity. The values for total alkalinity in samples E and F were found to slightly exceed the WHO standard (158 & 164 mg/l respectively). The bacteriological analysis (Total Coliforms, *Escherichia. Coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella typhi*) revealed that all the various water sources were in line with WHO recommendation as no isolate was found. This study therefore reveals that all the drinking water sources available to cadets of Nigeria Police Academy are safe and suitability for drinking as such can be termed potable water.

Keywords: Bacteriological, pathogenic microorganism, physicochemical, potable water, total coliform

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1.0 Introduction

Water is important to life on earth, it comprises 99% of our bodies and covers 71% of the earth's surface. It is essential to life where it is very important for the composition and restoration of cells (Abera et al. 2011) and critical for the survival of all living organisms. Thus, adequate supply of clean safe drinking water is required for the sustenance of life and also to prevent the outbreak of water-borne diseases.

The presence of potentially harmful, disease-causing (pathogenic) bacteria and other microorganisms is a concern when considering the safety of drinking water. Water-borne and water related diseases like cholera, typhoid fever, hepatitis A, schistosomiasis and dysentery can break out in any community that does not have access to safe water supply of adequate quantity. The most important and immediate effect to human health from using contaminated drinking water is diarrhea disease especially among children in poor countries [World Health Organization, 2007]. Studies have shown that over one billion people in the world lack access to potable drinking water and 2.5 billion people do not have access to adequate sanitation services (Tar et al., 2009) especially in

developing countries like Nigeria. Due to the inability of the government to meet the ever-increasing water demand, people resort to ground water sources such as shallow wells and boreholes as alternative water resources (LAWMA, 2000). Natural groundwater is usually of good quality but this can be contaminated due to inadequate source of protection and poor resource management.

Contamination of groundwater stems from different sources that include unsanitary condition during borehole construction, splashing of runoff into wells, flooding at borehole site, leachate from old burned waste pit or latrine into the hole through cracks in the aquifer closeness of borehole to septic tanks (Essien and Bassey, 2012). Also, there is the potential for natural levels of minerals and other chemicals to be detrimental to human health (Anawara et al., 2002). Chemical parameters of drinking water have the tendency to pose more of a chronic health risk, even though some components like nitrates and nitrites may have an acute impact. Physical parameters affect the appearance of the drinking water and might complicate the removal of microbial pathogens.

The ever-increasing demand for potable drinking water has led to the concept of packaged water (sachet and bottled). It is a general perception that

packaged water is safe for consumption. These packaged waters are usually subjected to one or more treatment methods which are intended to improve its safety and aesthetic quality. Most producers of packaged water source their raw water from well water which is usually contaminated either by fecal contamination from sepsis tank leakage or from soil and air contaminants. As such the raw water has to go through series of processes such as Filtration, Chemical processes (Chlorination, Flocculation e.t.c) and UV treatment in order to rid the water of any pathogen that may be present in it before the water can be packaged into any form.

The National Agency for Food and Drug Administration Agency (NAFDAC) has to certify these packaged water free from disease causing pathogens by testing the water for the presence of Indicator organisms (These are bacteria whose presence suggest fecal contamination of water, they include Coliforms, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Salmonella spp* e.t.c) before they can be distributed to the general populace. Also, some physicochemical parameters like pH, turbidity, temperature, dissolved oxygen, alkalinity must be checked as these parameters can affect the drinking water quality if their values are in higher concentrations than the safe limits set by the World Health Organization (WHO) and NAFDAC (WHO, 2011).

Research has shown that some distributed packaged water when examined did not meet up to NAFDAC standard but yet are still in distribution for example a study carried out by Oduyemi, (2015) suggests a high rate of contamination of packaged drinking water sold in Nigeria. Also various studies have been conducted to ascertain the physical, chemical and Microbiological qualities in varying drinking water sources, well water (Ezeribe et al., 2012; Mile et al., 2012; Aboh et al., 2015; Gambo et al., 2015; Allamin et al., 2015), borehole water (Ibe and Okpleny, 2005; Onwughara et al., 2013; Isa et al., 2013; Ukpong and Okon 2013; Sa'eed and Mahmoud, 2014; Ehiowemwenguan et al., 2014), lake (Okorundu and Anyadoh-Nwadike, 2015), packaged water (Ugochukwu et al., 2015; Halage et al., 2015) and stream/river water (Joshi et al., 2009; Lawal and Lohdip, 2015). It is on these bases that this research was conducted to determine the sanitary qualities of the various drinking water sources(sachet, bottled and borehole) available to cadets of Nigeria Police Academy, Wudil, Kano, Nigeria.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Sample collection:

Eight brands of packaged water [four each of sachet (labeled A-D) and bottled water (labeled E-H)] was bought from retail shops inside the Academy. Borehole water was also sourced from four different points (labeled I-L) inside the cadets' hostels. The borehole water was left to run for about 5mins and the water samples were collected in sterile 1.5litres bottles, preserved in ice packs and transported to the laboratory.

2.2 Physicochemical Parameters:

The pH was measured using a pH meter. The pH meter was first calibrated using buffer solutions (4.0, 7.0, 10.0) after which the pH of each water sample was determined by inserting the pH sensor into a measured volume of each sample. Total Dissolved Solids (TDS) was determined in two parts TDS A and TDS B. Part A was determined by measuring 10mls of the water sample into the titration bottle, three drops of methyl orange indicator was added, capped and swirled, until the color changes to yellow. This is then titrated against 0.75% HCL to get a color change from yellow to pink, after which the reading is taken and recorded. Part B was carried out using the same process but in a ion exchange resin column B and the color change to be observed is from pink to yellow.

Determination of Total Hardness (TH) was conducted by measuring 10cm³ of water pipetted into a conical flask. 1cm³ of buffer solution (NH₄Cl) with pH =10 and 3 drops of Erichrome black indicator were added to the flask. The mixture was then titrated with 0.01M ethyl diamine tetra acetic acid (EDTA) until the color changed from wine red to blue.

The determination of total alkalinity was done by measuring 100cm³ of water into a beaker where 2 – 3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator was added. Color change was observed following the titration with 0.1N HCl until the color changed from pink to colorless (FAO/WHO, 1997).

Dissolved Carbon dioxide (CO₂) was determined by measuring 100mls of the water sample into titration bottles and capped immediately. Two (2) drops of phenolphthalein indicator were added to the sample and swirled. The direct reading titrator was filled with CO₂ Reagent A and titrated drop wise against the water sample until a faint pink color, which persisted for thirty seconds is observed. The reading from the titrator was taken and recorded.

Nitrate content in water samples was measured using Nitrite A and B reagents in 10mls of water sample,

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followed by vigorous shaking to obtain a uniform mixture which was allowed to settle for 15 minutes for reaction to take place. The spectrophotometer was set and run at a wavelength of 890 nm and blanks were used for calibration and quality check. The various water samples were then measured using the spectrophotometer.

2.3 Bacteriological analysis: All the media for bacteriological analysis were prepared according to the Manufacturer's specification. The Most Probable Number (MPN) method was used to determine Total

coliforms in the samples using MacConkey agar. *Escherichia coli* was determined using Eosin methylene blue medium via pour plate technique. SSA (Shigella Salmonella Agar) medium and CTA (Centrimide Agar) medium were used for determining *Salmonella typhi* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* respectively via pour plates technique. SSA (Shigella Salmonella Agar) media was prepared according to manufacturer's instructions and it was sterilized on a Bunsen burner by allowing it to boil after which it was left to cool to about 35-45°C.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Results

Table 1: Result of physiochemical analysis

	Sachet Water				Bottled Water				Bore Hole				WHO STAN
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	
PH	7.68	8.03	7.6 2	7.56	8.18	7.80	6.83	8.08	6.52	6.38	6.55	6.50	6.5-8.5
Dissolved carbon (iv) oxide	17	18	23	43	14	30	40	29	6	47	30	36	50
Total Alkalinity (mg/l)	32	74	20	24	158	164	63	50	70	66	68	70	100
Total Hardness (mg/l)	6	44	4	16	16	86	20	28	31	37	34	37	100
Total Dissolved Solids (mg)	90	70	30	40	100	110	40	50	70	50	50	60	500
Nitrite	Nil	0.0528	Nil	0.0627	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	0.2

Table 2: Result of bacteriological analysis

SAMPLE	COLIFORM (cfu/ml)	E. COLI	PSEUDOMONAS	SALMONELLA
A	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G
B	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G
C	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G
D	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G
E	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G
F	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G
G	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G
H	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G
I	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G
J	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G
K	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G
L	O,O,O	N. G	N. G	N. G

Key: A - D = Different brands of sachet water that cadets drink, E - H = Different brands of bottled water that cadets drink. I - L = Bore hole water sourced from different locations in Police Academy, N.G = No Growth mg/l, Total Dissolved Solids within 30-110 mg/l, and Nitrate within 0.0528-0.0627.

All the physical and chemical composition of the various drinking water sources was within the WHO standard limits except for Total Hardness in sample E and F where the results exceeded the WHO limit. The pH of the water samples was within the range of 6.38-8.18, Dissolved CO₂ within 6-47l, Total Alkalinity within 20-164, Total Hardness within 4-86

All water samples passed the bacteriological test as there was no growth in any of the plates and no gas formation in tubes to indicate presence of coliforms.

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3.2 *Discussion:* Potable water should be free from chemicals and microorganisms; its physical state must meet with the generally acceptable standard. The physical parameters analyzed in all the water samples include odour, taste and colour and all the samples passed for these three physical parameters. These quality assessing parameters affects the acceptability of water for consumption (Yakasai and Atiku, 2010). For the sachet and bottled water, this could be as a result of the filtration methods involving sand and activated carbon filtration employed during sachet water production by most companies.

Drinking water with pH range of 6.5 to 8.5 is generally considered satisfactory (WHO, 2011). When the water is too acidic or alkaline it can lead to acidosis or alkalosis. The pH of all the water samples fell within the WHO limit, and this result is similar to that reported by Sa'eed and Mahmoud (2014) and Allamin et al. (2015). Low pH could result in the metallic taste frequently associated with some packaged water. High levels are undesirable since they may impact a bitter taste to the water (Safe Drinking Water Committee, 2005).

The Dissolved Carbon dioxide obtained for the various samples were within the WHO limits and this indicates low activity of microbes in the water as CO₂ is introduced in a water sample as a result of the activities of micro organisms. Total alkalinity level obtained from this research shows that the alkalinities of all the water samples tested were relatively low except for sample D and E (158 & 164). The constituents of alkalinity in natural systems include mainly carbonate, bicarbonate and hydroxide (Manivasakam, 1996) and it is a measure of the capacity of water to neutralize acids or hydrogen ions. Alkalinity is not considered harmful to humans but is generally associated with water hardness and excess dissolved solids (World Health Organization, 2006). Water with high alkalinity may also have a distinctly flat, unpleasant taste (World Health Organization, 2006).

Results of the Total dissolved solids test were within the acceptable limit of 500 mg/l as recommended by WHO. This is similar to that obtained in Owerri and Lagos Metropolis by Nwosu et al. The source of TDS in drinking water is attributed to natural sources, domestic wastewater, runoffs and industrial wastewaters. Water with high levels of TDS may cause excessive scaling in water pipes, heaters, boilers and household appliances while those with

extremely low values may have a distinctly flat taste (Bruvold & Ongerth, 1996).

The total hardness of the water samples obtained was within the recommended limit of 100 mg/l, given by WHO. World Health Organization classified every water <100 mg/l CaCO₃ as soft and >100 mg/l CaCO₃ as hard. All the water samples in the study were soft and fit for consumption. This is in line with the result obtained from a similar work carried out in Nsukka town by Onweluzo et al. Calcium and magnesium dissolved in water are the two most common minerals that make water "hard." The degree of hardness becomes greater as the calcium and magnesium content increases. Nitrate was only observed in two of the water samples (sample B and D) after a qualitative test. Quantitative tests then reveal that the value of the nitrate was below the limit given by WHO (0.2). Presence of nitrogen in the form of nitrates indicates older events of pollution and does not represent an immediate threat (World Health Organization, 1984). According to WHO (2004), nitrate and its conversion products may enter groundwater from the excessive application of fertilizers, leaching of waste water and other organic wastes. The Bacteriological test carried out on all the various sources of drinking water showed that there was no coliform, E. coli, Pseudomonas and Staphylococcus spp. This is indicative of good production practice and adherence to the guidelines given by WHO for the production of packaged water by the different producers of the sachet and bottled water. Also, for the boreholes, it shows that they were not dug close to septic tanks nor are they exposed to contamination from anthropogenic sources.

Conclusion

Overall, this study reveals that all various sources of drinking water sampled were in conformity with stipulated standards (NAFDAC and WHO) and are safe for drinking. However, this result is only a reflection of the state of the water sampled as at the time when the studies were conducted. Therefore, it is important that studies like this be done periodically in order to ensure that the various drinking water available to cadets, staff and the entire community of the Nigeria Police Academy is safe at all times.

Authors' Contribution

Babarinde O Rachel - Conception and study design, Materials, Data Collection and Processing, Analysis and interpretation, Drafting of manuscript and Funding.. Hadiza Ali – Critical Review

Conflict of Interest

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I have no conflict of interest to declare

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